

COMPARISON OF IN-PLANE COMPRESSIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF HEXAGONAL AND AUXETIC HONEYCOMBS WITH FIBRE REINFORCEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

Auxetic structures present a viable method of enhancing the in-plane compression characteristics of honeycomb lattices. Here, hexagonal and re-entrant lattices have been compared under quasi-static compression. Given the inherent complexity of manufacturing an auxetic structure, 3D printing has been employed for specimen fabrication. Fibre reinforcements of Carbon Fibre and Fibreglass have been included in the vertical cell walls to provide stiffness in the direction parallel to loading. These reinforced specimens were then compared to a non-reinforced set. Specific energy absorption was found to improve when using the auxetic lattices. By reinforcing the structural walls, an increase in energy absorption was observed across all specimens, with the greatest enhancement offered by Carbon Fibre. Through the use of auxetic re-entrant structures, the in-plane compressive characteristics of honeycomb architectures may be improved.

1 INTRODUCTION

Sandwich panels are commonly employed to shield assets from blast loading or to dissipate energy in a high velocity impact event. Consequently, sandwich panels have been employed within a variety of industries, including the aerospace, defense, automotive and marine sectors. Conventional core materials currently include foams and simple cellular geometries, such as square cells or honeycombs [1]. Honeycomb structures can only provide appreciable stiffness and strength when loaded in the out-of-plane direction [2], Fig. 1, whilst their capacity to absorb blast loading, for example, is primarily achieved through in-plane deformation. A strategy for enhancing in-plane stiffness and strength is therefore required to improve honeycomb cores used for energy absorbing structural applications.

Figure 1: Sandwich panel with honeycomb core.

Recently, research has highlighted the benefits of auxetic structures for improved performance of honeycomb structures when loaded in-plane [3]. Auxetics describe a group of materials (a sub-group within meta-materials) which exhibit a counter-intuitive behaviour due to their negative Poisson's ratio.

Subsequently, when placed under an axial load an auxetic will expand orthogonally to the direction of loading. Because of this behaviour, auxetics have been found to offer enhanced energy absorption, shear and fracture resistance, as well as increased hardness [4]. Several auxetic structures have been reported in the literature, the most common of which is termed the “*re-entrant*” honeycomb. Fig. 2 shows how a re-entrant structure will react under an applied tensile load.

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of expanding auxetic “*re-entrant*” honeycomb under applied loading.

Additive manufacturing is often employed to construct auxetic lattices given the great degree of geometric freedom available. 3D printing [4-6] and selective electron beam melting [7] techniques have been reported as methods of manufacturing more complex geometries. However, the use of recently-developed composite 3D printers facilitates the production of complex geometries which are formed from the placement of embedded continuous fibres within a polymer matrix.

2 PRESENT STUDY

2.1 Specimen Design

This study investigates the comparison of conventional and auxetic honeycomb architectures under in-plane quasi-static compression. The specimens were composed of interconnected lattices with 5-unit cells in the x and y directions, as presented in Fig. 3. The corresponding geometry of the (a) hexagonal and (b) re-entrant cells are presented in Table 1. Throughout the experiments these lattices have been denoted as HC and RHC respectively. Both designs had a cell wall thickness of 3.2 mm and depth of 15 mm.

Figure 3: Honeycomb lattices investigating (a) non-auxetic and (b) auxetic architectures with corresponding units cells.

Dimension	Hexagonal	Re-entrant
a (mm)	7.8	15
b (mm)	7.8	7.5
θ (°)	30	30

Table 1: Geometric design of unit cells.

2.2 Materials, Manufacture and Mechanical Testing

Specimens were designed within CAD software before the 3D printing layout was determined using 3D printing software Eiger [8]. Three different material configurations were investigated. Firstly, both cellular designs were 3D printed using pure Nylon, denoted as N within experiments. These lattices were then compared to specimens that feature fibre-reinforced vertical cell walls. Reinforcement was applied to the vertical cell walls with fibre being laid down in a concentric manner, as shown in Fig. 4. These vertical cell walls are presented in Fig. 5 with fibre reinforcement shown in blue. The fibre reinforcements selected for this study include Carbon Fibre and Fibreglass, denoted as CF and FG respectively.

Figure 4: Internal 3D printing structure for cell wall reinforcements [8].

Figure 5: Reinforcement within vertical cell walls of (a) hexagonal and (b) re-entrant cells.

Test specimens were manufactured using the Markforged Mark Two 3D printer, before quasi-static compression was conducted. Samples were compressed using the Lloyd LS5 test machine up to 50% strain at a rate of 2 mm/min using a 5kN load cell. This study evaluates compressive energy absorption capability as the performance indicator. As each of the panels yield slightly different masses, specific energy absorption (SEA), Equation 1, has been calculated from the force-displacement curves of each specimen. A high SEA would indicate greater compressive properties for future sandwich applications.

$$SEA = \frac{\int_0^d F(\delta)d\delta}{m} \quad (1)$$

3 DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Fig. 6 presents the force-displacement curves comparing the non-auxetic and auxetic honeycomb structures for each of the materials tested. During compression, lattices were observed to fold sequentially until final densification was achieved. The initial linear portion of these graphs describe the linear elastic regions and deformation occurs uniformly. Following this, the peak force is observed and denotes the point at which plastic deformation occurs. This point corresponds to the first row of cells collapsing upon itself. A plateau region follows before the next peak, which corresponds to the next row of cells collapsing. Final densification occurs when the cell walls begin to touch and the curve rises sharply. Printing inconsistencies resulted in two of the pure Nylon specimens (N_HC_1 and N_RHC_1) failing prematurely. As a result, these curves do not follow the other specimens and so these specimens were subsequently removed from the study.

From Fig. 6 (a) the re-entrant structures yielded lower initial peak forces and plateau stresses before reaching final densification. Failure in the pure Nylon specimens was caused by buckling of the vertical

cellular walls. For the reinforced structures, additional stiffness in the loading direction results in differing failure mechanisms. Rather than cell walls buckling, fracture failure was observed at the joint between the reinforced vertical and unreinforced diagonal walls. As presented Figures 6 (b) and (c), the addition of reinforcements permits both structures to withstand greater forces than an unreinforced specimens. The re-entrant structures were found to yield larger peaks than the hexagonal, however visible peaks indicate the sequential failure of cell rows. This densification leads to improved energy absorption characteristics.

Figure 6: Force displacement histories of (a) Pure Nylon (b) Carbon Fibre reinforced Nylon and (c) Fibreglass reinforced Nylon.

Fig. 7 presents the averaged SEA for each of the lattices tested. As shown, the re-entrant structures yielded higher SEA values with 20.9%, 52.8% and 42.9% increases over their hexagonal counterparts for Nylon, Carbon Fibre reinforced Nylon and Fibreglass reinforced Nylon respectively. All hexagonal structures yield similar compressive characteristics despite the increased mass and costs associated with including fibre reinforcements. The greatest SEA was obtained by the re-entrant honeycomb with Carbon Fibre reinforced cell walls. Given the significant cost differential between the two, Fibreglass presents a more economically viable alternative for structural enhancement.

Figure 7: Specific energy absorption of the honeycomb and re-entrant lattices using Nylon, Carbon Fibre reinforced Nylon and Fibreglass reinforced Nylon.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

Within this study the compression characteristics of two different hexagonal lattices were compared. The auxetic lattice provides an improvement in in-plane energy absorption under a quasi-static compressive load. The effect of adding fibre-reinforced cell walls was also investigated and found to provide further enhancement. Future work will include the incorporation of such lattices as sandwich panel cores to provide blast and impact protection.

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